

Emerging Trends in Concrete 3D Printing and Their Real-World Impact: Architecture and Design

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Abstract

The construction industry is undergoing a transformative shift towards high-quality development, driven by advancements in industrialization, digitization, and intelligent methodologies. Among these innovations, 3D printing technology has emerged as a game-changer due to its advantages, including high automation, precision, consistency, and efficiency. These attributes have opened broad application prospects for 3D printing in construction. To deepen the understanding of concrete 3D printing technology, this article explores the latest developments and trends in the field. It provides a comprehensive review of research by scholars globally, highlighting significant advancements in material strength and water resistance achieved through technological innovation. Additionally, the paper identifies current challenges in concrete 3D printing and proposes strategies for improvement, aiming to accelerate the adoption and refinement of this transformative technology within the construction industry.

Keywords: *Concrete, 3D printing, architecture, technology application, constructability.*

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Introduction

The swift expansion of urbanization has led to a significant increase in the demand for concrete in building, with global yearly production surpassing 4 billion tones. This level of production highlights the significance of concrete as the foundation of contemporary infrastructure, encompassing buildings, bridges, highways, and dams (Zhao, et al., 2024). Nonetheless, the ecological consequences of such large production are significant. Studies on energy consumption and carbon emissions in construction indicate that concrete production requires significant energy and raw resources. Recent research indicates that the process constitutes roughly 7-8% of global carbon dioxide emissions, with the building manufacturing phase markedly impacting energy usage and resource depletion (Chen, et al., 2024; Fan, et al., 2024). The challenges of excessive energy use, considerable material waste, and the environmental impact of conventional concrete production underscore the necessity for creative solutions.

To address these challenges, academics and engineers are investigating sophisticated technologies, such as 3D printing, as a revolutionary substitute for traditional construction techniques. 3D printing, a defining breakthrough of the “Third Industrial Revolution”, provides exceptional precision, customization, and efficiency, positioning it as a promising technology for tackling sustainability issues in building (Rani, et al., 2024). Its utilization encompasses various fields, such as industrial design, aerospace, and engineering, where it has already transformed conventional manufacturing methods. The incorporation of 3D printing in concrete construction is significant due to its capacity to minimize waste, augment design flexibility, and promote energy efficiency (De Schutter, et al., 2018; Sovetova, & Calautit, 2024).

Research indicates that concrete 3D printing diminishes labor requirements and decreases overall carbon emissions by roughly 16% in comparison to conventional construction techniques (Mohammad, Masad, & Al-Ghamdi, 2020; Han, et al., 2021). The adoption of 3D concrete printing in the construction industry has demonstrated its feasibility for infrastructure, façade components, modular building support, staircases, outdoor furnishings, and intricate wall design applications. A viable 3D system comprises numerous aspects, of which the aforementioned printing materials constitute a minor component. A 3D concrete printing system comprises a concrete mixer linked by pipes to a pump that delivers the material to a printing nozzle, which executes the process until the final configuration of the 3D printed structure is achieved, as shown in Figure 1 (Alami, et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Schematic Representation of the 3D Concrete Printing Process

It can be seen in Figure 1 that the three principal phases of concrete 3D printing: 1) Concrete mixing, wherein cementitious substances (e.g., OPC, geopolymers) are amalgamated with aggregates, including recycled materials; 2) Concrete pumping, which entails the conveyance of the mixture to the nozzle; and 3) Printing, during which the material is deposited in successive layers to fabricate intricate architectural forms. Printed structures are also illustrated. In addition to environmental advantages, this technique facilitates the incorporation of alternative and recycled materials in the printing process, hence diminishing dependence on virgin raw materials. Furthermore, the incorporation of 3D printing facilitates the creation of intricate geometries and structures that would be challenging or unattainable by conventional techniques, hence broadening the scope of architectural and structural design. Notwithstanding these benefits, the implementation of 3D printing technology in concrete building presents certain problems, as:

- **Characteristics:** The mechanical properties of printed concrete, such as strength, durability, and load-bearing capacity, require further investigation to ensure reliability and safety.
- **Applications:** Limitations in scaling up 3D printing technology for extensive and complex construction projects remain a challenge.
- **Structure:** The long-term durability and resilience of structures built using 3D printing techniques are not yet fully understood.
- **Cost:** The significant upfront investment in 3D printing equipment poses a barrier to adoption, especially for small and medium-sized construction firms.
- **Material development:** The need for specialized and compatible materials for 3D printing adds to the cost and complexity, hindering widespread use.

Addressing such barriers is essential for the effective assimilation of 3D printing technology within the construction sector. The main contributions of this study are:

- This article offers a comprehensive examination of the principles, apparatus, and materials associated with concrete 3D printing technology.
- It analyses its uses in the construction industry, underscores breakthroughs achieved by global researchers, and contrasts it with traditional construction methods to assess its advantages and drawbacks.
- This study seeks to expedite the advancement and implementation of concrete 3D printing technology by tackling existing problems and suggesting enhancement solutions, thereby fostering a more sustainable and efficient construction sector.

Technology

3D printing, or additive manufacturing, has evolved as a revolutionary technology that fabricates three-dimensional objects from digital models through the sequential layering of materials. In contrast to conventional subtractive manufacturing methods that entail cutting or carving materials, 3D printing constructs objects incrementally, utilizing computer-aided design (CAD) models. This approach facilitates enhanced design freedom, minimizes material waste, and enables the fabrication of intricate geometries typically unachievable using traditional methods (Alqutaibi, et al., 2024).

The progress of 3D printing technology has a significant history, marked by several pivotal milestones. In 1986, Charles Hull introduced stereolithography (SLA), a technique that employs ultraviolet light to selectively harden liquid photopolymer resin. The SLA printer, created by Hull's

business 3D Systems, was the inaugural commercial 3D printer, transforming prototypes in sectors including healthcare, automotive, and aerospace. SLA is known for its accuracy and refined surface finishes, rendering it suitable for high-resolution applications (Pagac, et al., 2021).

Fused deposition modelling (FDM) developed in 1988, a technology that continues to be one of the most prevalent ways for 3D printing (Lalegani Dezaki, Mohd Ariffin, & Hatami, 2021). FDM operates by extruding thermoplastic material through a heated nozzle, depositing it along defined trajectories on the X and Y axes. The substance solidifies as it cools, and the procedure progresses incrementally layer by layer. FDM is extensively utilized owing to its cost-effectiveness, material adaptability, and appropriateness for prototyping and functional components.

In 1989, selective laser sintering (SLS) described, a technique that use a high-powered laser to consolidate powdered material into a solid form (Tabriz Ghanizadeh, et al., 2024). This method facilitates the development of intricate, self-sustaining structures without supplementary scaffolding, as uncentered powder functions as an inherent support framework. SLS is especially advantageous in sectors necessitating strong mechanical characteristics, such as aerospace and automobile production.

In the same year, layered object manufacturing (LOM) is created, introduced an additional dimension to additive manufacturing (Park, Tari, & Hahn, 2000; Benning, 2012). LOM use sheet materials as the primary input, adhering layers with adhesives and shaping them with lasers or blades. This method is more efficient and economical than several alternatives, rendering it appropriate for the production of large-scale products and molds.

Recent improvements in 3D printing technology have significantly enhanced its possibilities. Binder Jetting and Material Jetting have created new opportunities by integrating rapid manufacturing with multi-material and multi-color printing capabilities. Likewise, direct energy deposition (DED) and electron beam melting (EBM) have become prominent in sectors such as aerospace and healthcare due to their capacity to produce dense metal components with outstanding mechanical characteristics (Nazir, et al., 2023). Moreover, concrete 3D printing has arisen as a transformative application in the construction industry, providing substantial time and cost efficiencies while facilitating creative architectural concepts.

The proliferation of 3D printing has surged significantly, with global industry sales projected to surpass \$50 billion by 2030 (Campbell, et al., 2011; Jiang, Kleer, & Piller, 2017). This expansion is propelled by its utilization in several sectors, such as healthcare (e.g., prostheses and implants), automotive (e.g., lightweight components), and consumer goods (e.g., customized products). Furthermore, progress in materials research has unveiled novel printable materials, including biopolymers, ceramics, and composite blends, thereby expanding the range of 3D printing applications.

Notwithstanding these gains, difficulties persist. The mechanical characteristics of printed components, particularly in load-bearing applications, necessitate additional optimization. Moreover, the expense of premium equipment and the creation of sophisticated materials can be too burdensome for smaller enterprises. Nevertheless, continuous research and invention are progressively surmounting these obstacles, rendering 3D printing an ever more feasible and disruptive technology. This article will examine these technologies thoroughly, offering an in-depth explanation of their principles, uses, and future possibilities, while emphasizing significant breakthroughs and ongoing issues in the field. Table 1 shows the advantages and disadvantages of the four printing technologies mentioned above (Shahrubudin, Lee, & Ramlan, 2019; Jiménez, et al., 2019).

Table 1. Advantages and Disadvantages of Printing Technologies

No.	Key technologies	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	SLA	High precision and smooth surface finishes. Ideal for complex and detailed structures.	Limited material compatibility. High costs for equipment and photopolymer resin. Slow process.
2	FDM	Cost-effective and widely available. Easy to use and maintain. Wide material options, including thermoplastics.	Poor surface finish compared to other methods. Limited strength for load-bearing applications.
3	SLS	No need for support structures. High mechanical strength. Suitable for intricate and durable designs.	High energy consumption. Expensive equipment and materials. Requires post-processing.
4	LOM	Fast production of large-scale objects. Low material costs. Ideal for prototyping molds and patterns.	Limited to sheet materials. Lower precision compared to other methods. Weak interlayer adhesion.
5	Binder Jetting	High-speed printing. Compatible with a wide range of materials. Low equipment cost compared to others.	Requires post-processing for strength. Limited mechanical properties. Lower density in printed objects.

Concrete 3D Printing

With the continuous improvement of architectural design and construction technology, as well as the continuous development of prefabricated buildings, the traditional methods of on-site mixing and pouring concrete have been largely replaced by prefabricated components and prefabricated buildings (Gunawardena, & Mendis, 2022). Applying 3D printing technology to the construction industry can open up new development space for future design and manufacturing.

The contour forming process, D-shape process, and concrete 3D printing process are the three major processes of architectural 3D printing. Khoshnevis et al. (2004) proposed the contour forming process, which uses computer-controlled material extrusion and a nozzle with a trowel to trim the printed contour, creating smoother buildings. Cesaretti et al. (2014) proposed the D-shape process in 2004 and invented the world’s first large-scale building 3D printer in 2010. Its working principle is that the nozzle alternately sprays particles and deposits them. For example, the printer first sprays magnesium adhesive, and then sprays sand on the adhesive, alternately spraying to form a solid building. Gosselin et al. (2016) proposed a concrete 3D printing process, based on FDM technology, using concrete material instead of thermoplastic as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Concrete 3D Printing Process

Source: Gosselin et al. (2016)

Add appropriate proportions of cementitious materials, aggregates, water, or admixtures to the concrete mixer to prepare concrete, and model the object design on the computer. Send system commands to control the robotic arm, extrude concrete through the nozzle, and finally manufacture the designed concrete component. Table 2 shows the characteristics of the three major processes mentioned above (Lim, et al., 2012).

Table 2. Analysis of Characteristics of the Three Major Processes

Project	Contour forming process	D-shape process	3D printing technology
Do you need a mold	Yes	No	No
Printing materials	Specific concrete	Powdery substance	Ordinary concrete
Advantage	Smooth surface, fast printing speed	Capable of weathering, layer printing, and high printing strength	High printing intensity and degree of freedom
Disadvantage	Weak interlayer strength	The printing surface is rough and the speed is slow	Printing size is limited by the printer

In Table 2, compared with traditional concrete construction methods, concrete 3D printing technology has many advantages. In terms of construction freedom, concrete 3D printing technology has extremely high design freedom. Traditional concrete construction requires the use of templates to constrain its shape, while concrete 3D printing technology does not require template constraints and directly stacks concrete based on the design model, allowing for the construction of various complex geometric shapes. In terms of construction accuracy, for parts that require high precision during the construction process, concrete 3D printing technology can reduce or even eliminate the use of manual labor, eliminating the need for manual operation. Directly controlling mechanical equipment through computers can effectively control dimensional errors. In terms of construction speed, 3D printing technology not only has higher work efficiency compared to traditional construction, but the printing equipment can also work continuously for 24 hours. At the same time, the printed concrete material can achieve rapid molding, effectively reducing the construction period (Wang, et al., 2023). In terms of material utilization, concrete 3D printing technology strictly controls the amount of printing materials according to computer instructions, reduces the waste of concrete materials, increases material utilization, and thus reduces the generation of construction waste and environmental pollution. In terms of construction cost, concrete 3D printing technology reduces the use of labor and material waste, shortens the construction period, and greatly reduces the construction cost (Volpe, et al., 2024; Tu, et al., 2023).

Practical Applications

Concrete 3D printing technology was first applied to small building printing. After Colla and Dini et al. (2013) invented the D-Shape printer, he made a bold attempt to print a lunar base, as shown in Figure 3 (a). Subsequently, architecture gradually applied to building construction, prefabricated component production, as well as landscape, garden and other scenes. Currently, concrete 3D printing technology is mainly used as a supplementary means to traditional building construction. Currently, 3D printed concrete is widely used in housing construction. In 2014, Shanghai Yingchuang Construction Company printed 200 m² 3D printed buildings in Qingpu Garden, as shown in Figure 3 (b). This is the first batch of 3D printed building complexes in China, constructed using recycled concrete 3D printing, with the entire printing process taking only 24 hours.

Figure 3(a). 3D Printing of Lunar Base

Figure 3(b). 3D Printed Architecture - Qingpu Garden

3D printing concrete technology has been widely applied in bridge construction. In 2017, Eindhoven University of Technology built a reinforced prestressed concrete bridge in Haimer, Netherlands. The bridge is 8 meters long and 3.5 meters wide, and is printed in 6 sections. After printing, the bridge is assembled on site and tensioned with prestressed steel bars to form a whole. Its construction speed is three times that of traditional construction speed (Salet, et al., 2018), as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Helmert Bridge in the Netherlands

The construction method of 3D printed bridges is simple, requiring only factory prefabrication and on-site assembly. It has the advantages of short construction time and material saving, and can be widely used in small bridges and landscape bridges in the future. In addition to its application in building and bridge construction, 3D printed concrete technology also has broad prospects in landscape construction. Concrete 3D printed applications such as chair and intelligent retaining wall are shown in Figure 5 (a) and (b), respectively.

(a) Chair

(b) Intelligent Retaining Wall

Figure 5. Concrete 3D Printed Applications

The combination of concrete 3D printing technology and information technology, such as AI and digital twin (Shoukat, et al., 2022; Shoukat, et al., 2024) has become a new application trend. It can be seen in Figure (b) that the intelligent retaining wall procedure they embedded sensors in the printed retaining wall structure, which can provide real-time temperature, strain, and pressure data. These data can effectively detect potential faults, and useful for digital twin modelling (Niaz, et al., 2022).

Challenges

Lack of Relevant Standards

Although the China Engineering Construction Standardization Association has released the T/CECS 786-2020 “Technical Specification for Concrete 3D Printing” in 2020, its scope is relatively narrow and cannot form a complete regulatory system.

High Requirements for Printing Materials

There are many restrictions on the selection of materials for 3D printing of concrete, which not only require the printed concrete to have good flowability, extrusion properties, etc., but also need to consider the material’s own strength, interlayer gaps, and bonding strength during the printing process.

Construction Size Limitations

In the horizontal direction, the construction size of concrete 3D printing is limited by the printing range and movable range of the printer. In the vertical direction, due to the influence of materials, concrete 3D printing is currently unable to print high-rise and super high-rise buildings in one go.

Printing Device Restrictions

Although 3D printing concrete technology can reduce costs during the construction process, significant investment is required in the early research of high-precision printing equipment. When the printer is built in situ, concrete 3D printing may also be affected by weather, site, and other factors, making it impossible to carry out production activities. If the concrete 3D printer is damaged, it will require funds for maintenance.

Lack of Technical Talent

At present, research on concrete 3D printing technology mainly focuses on the development of printing equipment and new materials, with little emphasis on the cultivation of technical talents, which is not conducive to the application of concrete 3D printing technology in practical engineering.

Suggestions

Before the large-scale commercial application of concrete 3D printing technology, it is urgent to establish a complete set of industry standards. The research results of experts and scholars should be transformed into detailed technical regulations, covering material requirements, acceptance standards, seismic and shock absorption, and other aspects, in order to build a comprehensive standard system. In addition, the application of concrete 3D printing technology is closely related to printing equipment, and the printing size of buildings is directly limited by the specifications of the printer. Therefore, it is necessary to accelerate the research and development of large-scale printing equipment and improve the mechanical performance of printers, such as waterproofing and mobility, to adapt to various complex construction environments. In the research and development of printing materials, it is necessary to ensure that the materials have basic printability while pursuing higher strength, even surpassing traditional concrete. Therefore, in the development of new materials, multiple materials such as solid waste materials and alloy materials are added to enrich the material selection of concrete 3D printing technology.

Although concrete 3D printing technology can help reduce manual labor, the printing quality largely depends on the operational level of technicians. From the installation, operation, adjustment to maintenance of the printer, every step requires careful control by professional personnel. Therefore, standardized training for printing technicians is particularly important, and training efforts should be increased to improve the professional skills of operators. At the same time, considering the development trend of the era of the Internet of Everything, we should combine the concrete 3D printing technology with the Internet technology, make full use of the advantages of the Internet, such as convenience, efficiency and accuracy, and promote the concrete 3D printing technology to develop in a more practical and intelligent direction.

7. Conclusion

In comparison to conventional construction methods, concrete 3D printing technology offers numerous advantages, including substantial labour cost savings, enhanced construction efficiency, reduced construction timelines, minimised waste production and emissions, improved structural accuracy, and decreased overall construction expenses. Nonetheless, concrete 3D printing technology remains nascent, encountering several hurdles in its development and implementation. We assert that the ongoing advancements and innovations in printing equipment and materials will likely enable concrete 3D printing technology to supplant conventional construction methods, emerge as the predominant technology in national construction, foster sustainable development within the construction sector, and aid in environmental conservation and pollution mitigation.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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